

Highly Enantioselective Extraction of Phenylglycine by a Chiral Macrocyclic Receptor based on Supramolecular Interactions

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ABSTRACT: Using supramolecular interactions, a novel macrocyclic receptor is able to selectively extract zwitterionic phenylglycine from neutral aqueous solutions into chloroform with up to 91.8% ee. Modeling studies, NMR experiments and X-ray diffraction analysis were carried out to explain the high enantioselectivity observed.

Enantiopure amino acids are important building blocks in pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals and food and fragrance industries. While L amino acids are the components of proteins, D enantiomers have found interesting applications in antibiotics, chemotherapeutics, immunosuppressives, deodorants, fluorescent markers of DNA, sweeteners, pesticides, etc.¹ In fact 5% of the top 200 brand name drugs by retail sales in 2018 possessed a D amino acid in their structure.²

Many of the industrial production of amino acids rely in fermentation processes, which usually require large volumes of water, big fermenters capacity, strict sterility and costly methods for product recovery that boosts the capital investment.³ Attractive alternatives arise from asymmetric synthesis or simple racemic synthesis followed by a chiral resolution step. In the last years, enantioselective liquid-liquid extraction has appeared as an attractive option because of low energy consumption, recyclability, easy handling and easy scalability.⁴ This technique requires a chiral receptor able to transport one of the amino acid enantiomers from an aqueous phase to an organic phase (Figure 1A). How-

ever, this is a challenging task, due to the ionic nature of zwitterionic amino acids that make them highly hydrophilic and extremely soluble in aqueous solutions, thus increasing the energetic cost associated with their desolvation. Also, the receptor needs to be able to simultaneously associate the positively charged ammonium group and the negatively charged carboxylate group of the amino acids which are arranged in a specific tridimensional disposition. All these features increase the complexity of the receptor structure. Amino acid derivatization has been proposed as an option to facilitate the extraction; however, a further deprotection step that increases the cost of the process is required. In order to make it profitable, it would be more attractive to find a receptor able to directly extract zwitterionic amino acids from aqueous solutions with high selectivity. Crown ethers,⁵ guanidiniums,⁶ metal complexes,⁷ lanthanide complexes⁸ and BINOL-carbonyl hosts⁹ have been traditionally employed,⁴ although most systems possess moderate operational selectivities (Figure 1B, selected examples for zwitterionic phenylglycine).

Figure 1. (A) Enantioselective Liquid-Liquid Extraction concept. (R=chiral receptor). (B) Selected chiral receptors and selectivities (α) for zwitterionic phenylglycine (Phg). (C) Precedents in the group for anion recognition with a carbazole scaffold. (D) Novel chiral macrocyclic receptor based on a carbazole-BINOL scaffold.

We have previously reported¹⁰ a carbazole-based receptor **1** (Figure 1C) functionalized with two sulfonamide groups as H-bond sites for anion complexation. While excellent affinities were obtained for halide anions ($K_a = 7.9 \times 10^6 \text{ M}^{-1}$ for Cl^- in CHCl_3), a strong decrease in binding was observed for oxyanions. This behavior, according to the X-ray structural analysis and modeling studies,¹⁰ was attributed to the importance of the $\text{CH}\cdots\text{X}$ (halogen) interactions in the binding process and the steric hindrance and receptor conformational changes observed for oxyanion association. Trying to develop a more efficient synthetic host for oxyanions and eventually for zwitterionic amino acids, the macrocyclic structure **2** (Figure 1D) was designed with several improved features: (i) two more H-bond donor groups; (ii) the macrocyclic structure ensures a higher degree of preorganization reducing the entropic cost of association;¹¹ (iii) a chiral binaphthyl unit enables the enantioselective recognition of chiral anions and (iv) the steric hindrance around the sulfonamide NHs has been reduced replacing the bis(trifluoromethyl)anilines by ethylenediamines. Thus, anion binding can be expected in the hydrogen bonding donor pocket of the preorganized receptor **2**, while chiral BINOL building block should be able to preferentially select one of the enantiomers. Also, (i) sulfonamide based carbazole receptors provide more acidic NHs than carboxamides and hence, potentially stronger associates; (ii) do not require transition metals and (iii) their synthesis can be easily carried out on a multigram scale from inexpensive starting materials. Herein, we wish to report our findings.

The synthetic strategy for the preparation of compound **2** was a convergent synthesis where ring closure could be achieved by the simultaneous formation of two sulfonamide bonds. While two different approaches were considered (disconnections *a* and *b*), as shown in Scheme 1a, route *a* afforded macrocycle **2** in higher yield (36% vs 25% in route *b*). As illustrated in Scheme 1b, starting from the readily available 3,6-di-*tert*-butyl-9*H*-carbazole **3**¹² and 2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl **4**,¹³ the synthesis of **2** was straightforward, involving as key intermediates the disulfonyl dichlorides **5**¹⁰ and **8**,^{5c} previously synthesized by our group. NMR experiments were carried out to unambiguously assign the chemical shifts for protons, both in CDCl_3 and in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ solvents (Figures S9-S18).

Scheme 1. (a) Synthetic strategies leading to macrocycle **2**. (b) Synthesis of the racemic macrocycle **2** via route *a*.

The anion binding affinity of racemic macrocycle **2** was explored and compared to acyclic receptor **1** by ^1H NMR titrations in CDCl_3 as solvent (Figures S19-S21). Halide and acetate anions were selected to compare with previous results obtained with receptor **1**.¹⁰

Table 1. Association constants K_a (M^{-1}) for the complexes formed by macrocycle **2** and receptor **1** and selected anions (added as tetrabutyl or tetraethyl ammonium salts) at 298 K in CDCl_3 . Errors estimated to be $\leq 10\%$.

Entry	Anion	Receptor 1	Receptor 2
1	Cl^-	7.9×10^{6a}	8.0×10^{5b}
2	I^-	4.2×10^{5a}	5.0×10^{5b}
3	AcO^-	<i>c</i>	2.8×10^5

^aMeasured by fluorescence. ^bMeasured by ^1H NMR competitive titration with receptor **1**. ^cData could not be fitted to a binding model due to the possible deprotonation of the receptor **1** by acetate.

While receptors **1** and **2** were found to display similar high affinities for halides (Table 1, entries 1 and 2), macro-

cycle **2** was able to bind acetate with an association constant higher than 10^5 M^{-1} (Table 1, entry 3). Thus, the replacement of the bis(trifluoromethyl)aniline by ethylenediamine in the sulfonamide linkages proved to be effective to avoid deprotonation (previously observed for receptor **1**), resulting in acetate binding through H-bonds.

Encouraged by these results, we next explored the association of amino acids in their zwitterionic form. While macrocycle **2** combines an oxyanion hole moiety¹⁴ for binding of carboxylates and a binaphthyl unit to impart chirality, ammonium binding was achieved using 18-crown-6 ether.¹⁵ Thus, the ability of this system to extract zwitterionic amino acids from aqueous solution into a chloroform phase was studied.^{5c}

In a typical liquid-liquid extraction experiment, a saturated aqueous solution of the amino acid was added to a solution of macrocycle **2** and 18-crown-6 ether in CDCl_3 , followed by vigorous stirring.¹ ^1H NMR analysis of the organic phase was used to estimate the extraction efficiency (Table 2, Figures S22-S34).

Table 2. Extraction of zwitterionic amino acids from aqueous solution into CDCl_3 by combination of macrocycle **2 and 18-crown-6 ether.**

Entry	Amino acid ^a	Extraction ^b (%)
1	D,L-alanine	-
2	D,L-leucine	-
3	D,L-phenylalanine	Quant. (56.4% ee) ^c
4	D,L-phenylglycine	Quant. (91.8% ee) ^c
5	D,L-serine	-
6	D,L-tryptophan	-
7	D,L-tyrosine	-
8	D,L- valine	-

^a0.5 mL of an aqueous saturated solution of the amino acid was added to 0.5 mL of a CDCl_3 solution of **2** ($1.15 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$) and 18-crown-6 ether ($2.65 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$), followed by vigorous stirring and centrifugation. ^bSingle extraction experiment; extraction percentages based upon the macrocycle concentration in the organic phase and determined by integration of the ^1H NMR signals. ^cDetermined by HPLC when receptor (*S*)-**2** is used.

Macrocycle **2** proved to be highly selective for aromatic amino acids phenylglycine and phenylalanine which were quantitatively extracted into CDCl_3 with 1:1 macrocycle to amino acid binding stoichiometry (Figures S32, S36, S38); the rest of the tested amino acids were not extracted to any measurable extent. Figure 2 displays the aromatic region of the ^1H NMR spectra of macrocycle **2** before (a) and after the extraction with a saturated solution of D-phenylglycine (b) and D-phenylalanine (c), where the appearance of the aromatic ring signals of both amino acids can be observed.

Amino acid recovery from the chloroform phase was easily achieved by removing the aqueous phase and washing the organic phase with one equivalent of potassium decanoate in water. 18-crown-6 ether traces were eliminated by washing twice the aqueous phase with chloroform (Figure S38).

Figure 2. Partial ^1H NMR spectra of macrocycle (*S*)-**2** before (a) and after liquid-liquid extraction with a saturated solution of D-phenylglycine (b) and D-phenylalanine (c).

The fact that, among the natural amino acids tested, only phenylalanine was extracted, could be used in the preparation of food supplements for the treatment of Phenylketonuria.¹⁶

The observed selectivity in the extraction of the underivatized amino acids prompted us to prepare the enantiopure receptor (*S*)-**2** starting from (*S*)-2,2'-dihydroxy-1,1'-binaphthyl **4**.¹⁷ While chiral macrocycle **2** was being synthesized, further evidence for enantioselective binding was obtained using a methodology our group has successfully applied for the resolution of racemic receptors.^{5c,18} Conventional TLC plates were impregnated with a 1.5% aqueous solution of L-phenylglycine and the stoichiometric amount of 18-crown-6 ether and dried. Elution of the racemic macrocycle afforded two separated spots, corresponding to the diastereomeric complexes of L-phenylglycine with each enantiomer of racemic **2**. At the same time, elution of (*S*)-**2** in TLC plates impregnated with L-phenylglycine and D-phenylglycine clearly showed that the strong complex is formed with D-phenylglycine, affording a spot with larger R_f than the spot generated after elution in the L-phenylglycine impregnated TLC (Figure S41).

These preliminary results were later confirmed by the liquid-liquid extraction experiments with the enantiopure macrocycle (*S*)-**2** and the racemic amino acids. To our delight, analysis by chiral HPLC showed a preference of macrocycle (*S*)-**2** for D-enantiomers, reaching a 91.8%ee for phenylglycine (Table 2, entry 4) and 56.4%ee for phenylalanine (Table 2, entry 3). The selectivity obtained for zwitterionic phenylglycine ($\alpha = 11.2$) is, to our knowledge, the best result for this amino acid obtained so far.

To understand the origin of this enantiodiscrimination, NMR studies were carried out on the diastereomeric complexes of receptor (*S*)-**2** with L- and D-phenylglycine in the presence of 18-crown-6-ether. The chemical shifts for selected protons are displayed in the ESI (Table S1, Figures S33-S39) and show that the carbazole NH is not involved in the binding with the amino acid while the carbazole sulfonamide NHs are shifted from 5.57 ppm to 8.59 and 8.43 ppm in the complexes, as expected when H-bonds are formed (Figure 2). It is remarkable the very different chemical shifts for the *meta* protons of both enantiomers of phenylglycine

in the complexes, which seems to indicate different geometries for the associates. This hypothesis was also corroborated by the ^{13}C NMR spectra of the two diastereomeric complexes, where differences in chemical shifts were observed for some of the macrocycle carbons (Figure S39).

X-ray crystallographic analysis turned to be a powerful tool to clarify the geometry of the complexes. When an equimolar mixture of racemic macrocycle **2**, racemic phenylglycine and 18-crown-6 ether were dissolved in a chloroform/methanol solution, crystals of the ternary complexes 1:1:1 were obtained, with the configurations (*S*)-**2**•D-phenylglycine and (*R*)-**2**•L-phenylglycine (Figure 3, S46-S48).

Figure 3. X-ray structure of the ternary complex (*S*)-**2**•D-phenylglycine•18-crown-6 ether with hydrogen bonds as yellow dotted lines. For clarity the ternary complex is shown in two views: amino acid and macrocycle (above) and amino acid with crown ether (below). The dihedral angles of the ethylenediamine groups are shown in the top-right view.

The X-ray structure shows that the carboxylate is bound to the macrocycle through three H-bonds: two formed with both carbazole sulfonamides (Table S4, entries 1 and 2) and the third one with one of the binaphthyl sulfonamides (Table S4, entry 3). The fourth sulfonamide NH is not involved in the binding, pointing outside the cavity. As expected, the ammonium group is encapsulated by the crown ether, forming several H-bonds. The crown ether is tilted toward the H atom in the amino acid, to prevent steric interactions with the larger α -carbon substituents (Figure 3, bottom). In addition, two intramolecular H-bonds are formed in the macrocycle, between the carbazole NH and one of the oxygen atoms of the sulfonamide linked to the carbazole ring (2.450 Å and 2.466 Å).

The phenyl substituent is located in the gap left by the binaphthyl group; the conformation adopted by the nearest ethylene diamine (Figure 3, top-right), which directs the fourth NH out of the cavity, contributes to enlarge this gap. In addition, the upfield shift of the phenylglycine *meta* ^1H signals (6.74 ppm) in the (*S*)-**2**•D-phenylglycine complex

can be attributed to the proximity of these protons to the binaphthyl aromatic sheet (Table S1).

Since no crystals were obtained for the weak complex, DFT calculations were performed to explain the enantioselectivity (see details in the ESI). The structure of the most stable (*S*)-**2**•D-phenylglycine complex (Figure 4) is similar to the X-ray structure. For the (*S*)-**2**•L-phenylglycine complex, two structures were found. The first one shows the carboxylate and the phenyl group occupying the same positions that in the strong complex, leading the H substituent (and the bulky crown ether that is tilted toward it) in the direction of the other binaphthyl sheet. Alternatively, the gap which is occupied by the phenyl group in the stronger complex can be used to accommodate the amino substituent bound to the crown ether. The latter structure is 2.3 kcal/mol more stable, but still is highly destabilized with respect to the (*S*)-**2**•D-phenylglycine complex (7.9 kcal/mol). A similar study on the complexes with phenylalanine shows a smaller energy difference (4.5 kcal/mol).

Figure 4. DFT optimized structures for the complexes of (*S*)-**2** and phenylglycine.

In conclusion, we have shown that using supramolecular interactions, a new chiral macrocyclic receptor is able to selectively extract zwitterionic phenylglycine from aqueous solutions with high enantioselectivity. X-ray diffraction and DFT studies analysis explained the high enantiodiscrimination observed and will be helpful to further improve the receptor design in a near future.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website.

Experimental procedures, spectroscopic data, NMR titrations and extraction experiments, HPLC chromatograms, ORTEP diagrams, X-ray crystal structure data and modelization studies (PDF).

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Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

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